

CARBON/GRAPHITE FOAMS FOR STRUCTURAL AND THERMAL MANAGEMENT APPLICATIONS

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SUMMARY: The inherent properties of carbon/graphite in an open cell foam architecture has potential for a plethora of applications relative to lightweight, thermal conductivity, inertness, surface area, resistivity, fluid flow, etc. A domestic source of coal tar pitch (CTP) has been identified as a low cost precursor to produce high quality carbon/graphite foams and as a component to produce SiC foam. Foam compressive strengths of over 4,000 psi have been attained. The thermal conductivity can be varied from under 1 W/mK to over 200 W/mK, as well as the density varied from 0.16 g/cm³ (1 lb/ft³) to 0.75 g/cm³ (47 lb/ft³). Carbon/Graphite foam has been infiltrated with polymers, aluminum, and copper for highly dampened structures, and with high thermal conductivity and low expansion. Discussion will include foam processing, properties, and applications.

KEY WORDS: foam, processing, thermal conductivity, microstructure, properties.

INTRODUCTION

Since the discovery that graphite foam could be produced from pitch by Kearns [1, 2] at the Air Force and latter by James Klett at Oak Ridge National Laboratory (ORNL) [3], there has been a desire to define a low-cost, domestic source for the pitch precursor. A significant effort has been devoted to correlate the materials/process/property relationships to produce foams with customized properties that exhibited lightweight, and exemplary thermal and structural properties and meets diverse applications. The primary objective of this work was to correlate the materials/process/property relationships utilizing a low-cost domestic source pitch. The pitch precursor critically influences processing parameters for producing graphite foam that meets a diversity of application requirements. The initial and base processing was the Air Force process under license to MER from the Air Force. Although the applications for carbon foam are still very much in the formative stages, several initial applications have been identified. These include high thermal conductivity for several thermal management applications, low thermal conductivity for insulation applications, ultra-lightweight structural dampening, energy absorbance, mirror bases and catalyst carriers, just to mention a few.

In high performance electronics, packaging is the limiting factor in electrical circuit efficiency. Specifically, thermal management, along with reliability and the trend toward miniaturization, are key factors in successful electronic design [4-6]. A common problem in the design of microelectronic packages, however, is that material candidates having high thermal conductivity also have a high Coefficient of Thermal Expansion (CTE). For example, copper has a thermal conductivity of about 400 W/m²K; however, the CTE of copper is about $16.5 \times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$. Thus, a metal substrate containing a high concentration of copper yields unacceptable results in most microelectronics applications compared to metal substrates made of a single metal or metallic alloy. Porous graphite-foam has been demonstrated to exhibit high thermal conductivity and low CTE. Metal matrix composite (MMC) carrier substrates can be better designed to match the thermal expansion characteristics of the chip or other heat-generating component attached to the carrier substrate, while also providing improved heat transfer. This work describes an innovative Cu/graphite-foam MMC process.

Lightweight silicon carbide (SiC) optics and structures have the potential to play a significant role in exploring the structure and evolution of the universe. State-of-the-art SiC optics is limited by the weight of fully dense monolithic SiC. The lower limit areal density using monolithic SiC is limited to approximately 25 kg/m². SiC foam has been investigated to reduce weight, which was produced by sealing the surface of the SiC foam with a chemically vapor depositing (CVD) layer. The objective of this effort was to overcome the limitations of state-of-the-art SiC optics by developing an isotropic SiC foam that is functionally graded to a dense SiC surface and can be optically polished.

EXPERIMENTAL

A standard 150 °C softening point Coal Tar Pitch (CTP) was utilized for processing carbon foam for structural applications. Mitsubishi AR pitch was also utilized to produce foam for high thermal conductivity applications. All of the AR pellets were ball-milled for about 10 hours using aluminum oxide grinding media and screened through sieves. High purity oxygen free copper pellets were used for MMC infiltration. Silicon powder was purchased from Elchem and was screened to –200 mesh before being used as the raw material for SiC foam.

Since the foaming is carried out under high pressure, the pressure vessels were designed using high strength steel with very thick walls in order to sustain the high pressure at high temperature. The pressure vessels are connected to nitrogen cylinder with pressure relief valve to control the internal pressure. A pressure relieve valve is connected to the pressure vessel so that when the gas expands during the heat up step, the pressure can be maintained at a desired level. Thermal gravimetric analysis (TGA) was tested for weight loss and decomposition as a function of temperature. The testing environment was under nitrogen atmosphere to prevent the carbon/graphite from being oxidized and the heating rate was maintained at 10 °C/minute in order to minimize the time lag between DTA and TGA curves. Dilatometry thermal analysis was performed to measure the thermal expansion coefficient (CTE) of the foams and metal matrix composites.

Conventional infiltration was used to infiltrate the copper into the graphite foams. The infiltration was performed at 1200 °C for 2 hours in a pure H₂ atmosphere. Thermal diffusivity was measured using a Laser Flash technique [7] at room temperature. The sample size is approximately 1/2”x1/2”x1/2”. The transient temperature-time response of the back face was measured and analyzed to give the value for the thermal diffusivity. The Laser Flash thermal conductivity measurement was used to measure the thermal diffusivity, which was then used to calculate the thermal conductivity using the equation: $\kappa = \rho \cdot \lambda \cdot C_p$, where κ : Thermal Conductivity, ρ : Density, λ : Thermal Diffusivity, C_p : Heat Capacity. The heat capacity for graphite and copper are approximately 0.70 and 0.385 J/gK, respectively, based on the Handbook of Chemistry.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

1. Carbon Foams

The 150 °C softening point CTP has too high a volatile content to produce a uniform pore structure foam. In this work, the CTP was refined with heating and stirring that increases softening point. The refined CTP was designated as CTP1. Since the foaming mechanism of pitch is to eliminate the volatile during a liquid phase that must turn to solid to fix the foam structure, it is desirable to identify its response to heating based on thermal gravimetric analysis (TGA). Figure 1 shows the TGA curves of the CTP1 along with that of an as received CTP and AR pitch. As can be seen from figure 1, for raw CTP,

the volatile starts to volatilize at about 200 °C and increases significantly between 300 to 500 °C. While for CTP1 and AR pitches, the volatile starts at much higher temperature, 275 °C. The amount of volatile increases significantly between 400 to 500 °C and then slows down when temperature is further increased. The weight loss decreases substantially at approximately 500 °C for all three pitches. The raw CTP has a total volatile content of more than 50 wt%, which is much higher than CTP1 and AR pitch at about 30 to 33 wt% range. The refined CTP (CTP1) has a very similar volatile content and decomposition characteristics to AR pitch. Since foaming is created by the release of gas with the surrounding structure becoming solid, the temperature and rate of heating versus volatile loss is a first order primary variable for generating a foam structure. The size of the gas bubble, which forms the pores of the foam directly, affects the foam density.

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 Figure 1: TGA curves of raw CTP, CTP1 and AR pitch (4 °C/min. N₂).

Figure 2 show the compressive strengths as a function of foam density for both AR and CTP1 pitch. Both foams were carbonized at 1000 °C. From Figure 2, it is obvious that as the density of the foam increases, the compressive strength increases. The reason for this is due to the thicker ligaments, which have a much higher strength as well as smaller pores and thus shorter length ligaments. In addition, CTP1 has higher compressive strength throughout the entire foaming pressing range compared to AR pitch foam. The difference in strength between the pitch precursors seems to be larger as the density increases. This is evident from the fact that when the density is about 0.75 g/cm³, the strength of CTP1 foam is about 4 times higher than that of AR pitch foam.

Figure 2: Effect of density on compressive strength for CTP1 and AR pitch foams.

Figures 3(a) and 3(b) are SEM micrographs showing the typical microstructure of AR foam and CTP1 foam, respectively, that were heat treated to 1000 °C. As can be seen in 3(a), the microstructural characteristic shows that the AR microstructure consists of a laminated structure that lacks bonding between the formed crystals. Figure 3(b) shows a more equi-axial crystal morphology for CTP1, which appears to be well bonded. The CTP1 seems to possess more of a solid bridge, which may, at least in part, account for the higher strength, compared to AR pitch foam.

(a)

(b)

Figure 3: SEM micrographs showing the ligaments of (a) AR foam and (b) CTP1 foam.

2. Thermal Management Applications

To enhance the thermal conductivity, an AR pitch foam with 0.78 g/cm^3 was heat treated at $3000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. When the carbon foam is graphitized at high temperature, a highly aligned graphite structure is obtained. A thermal conductivity of 215 W/mK has been achieved at a foam density of 0.78 g/cm^3 . However, this high thermal conductivity is only in the Z-direction with respect to foaming process. The thermal conductivity along the X and Y directions were 58 and 60 W/mK , respectively. The mechanism for the anisotropic thermal conductivity can be explained in the microstructural examination.

Figures 4(a) and 4(b) are SEM micrographs showing the graphitic ligaments after heat-treated at 3000°C . The difference between figures 4(a) and 4(b) can be explained based on the foaming process. Foaming utilizing the basic Air Force technology starts with ground pitch powders and with the release of volatiles, the foam rises toward the top of the container. Assuming the top and bottom is the Z-direction, the X-Y direction would be the horizontal iso-plane. Figure 4(a) was taken from the Z-direction while figure 4(b) was taken from the X-Y direction. The AR pitch ligaments or struts have somewhat of a non-connected structure that consists of individual fibrous microstructure. The most important feature is that most of the graphite ligaments are aligned along the Z-direction. For covalent bond materials, phonon transmission is the mechanism for the thermal conductivity. Any defects caused by impurities, dislocation, residual stress, and interfaces tend to contribute to phonon scattering. With the three dimensional ligament structure, the graphite foam can have minimum interference to the phonon transmission and achieves a high thermal conductivity.

(a)

(b)

Figure 4: SEM micrographs showing the graphitization structure after $3000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ heat treatment (a) Z direction and (b) X-Y direction.

Figure 5 shows the X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) patterns of AR pitch foam heat treated at 3000 °C. As can be seen from figure 5, the high temperature heat treatment not only eliminated all of the residual volatiles but also transformed the amorphous carbon into a graphite phase. When the foam is subsequently turned into graphite at high temperature, a highly aligned graphite structure is obtained. CTE was calculated using dilatometer curve tested in nitrogen. The CTEs for the graphitized AR pitch foam are 2.5, 2.6, 2.8, and 3.1 $\times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$ for temperature ranges between RT to 200, 400, 600, and 800 °C, respectively.

Figure 5: X-Ray diffraction patterns showing the high degree of graphitization at 3000 °C.

It is well established that graphite does not wet copper, which makes it difficult to infiltrate the graphite foam with molten copper. To overcome the non-wetting characteristics, a pressure-assisted infiltration was performed. The threshold pressure for the infiltration of melt through the open channels depends on (1) the contact angle between the melt and particles and (2) pore size of the foam. Figure 6 is the SEM micrograph showing graphite form infiltrated with high purity copper performed at 1200 °C with an inert gas overpressure. Figure 7 shows the XRD of the infiltrated composite. As can be seen from this figure, there is no interaction between copper and graphite foam to form any intermediate compounds. Table 2 summarizes the properties of the infiltrated copper/graphite-foam MMC.

Figure 6: SEM micrograph showing the microstructure of the graphite foam infiltrated with high purity copper.

Figure 7: XRD showing the individual copper and graphite phases without any intermediate phase reaction.

Table 2: Properties of the infiltrated Cu/Graphite-foam MMC.

Properties	Density (g/cm ³)	Thermal Conductivity (W/mK)			CTE ($\times 10^{-6}/^{\circ}\text{C}$)			
		X	Y	Z	RT to 200 °C	RT to 400 °C	RT to 600 °C	RT to 800 °C
Value	1.85	146	148	351	5.2	5.5	5.9	6.5

3. SiC Foam

Preceramic SiC polymers can be used to form SiC by heat treating in an inert atmosphere at high temperature. The SiC material obtained by this approach has an isotropic structure without any binder phases. Also, the volatiles from these preceramic polymers tend to form small pores under pressure. Since pitch readily foams, a refined coal tar pitch (CTP1) and a pre-ceramic precursor was mixed in order to improve the pore structure of the foam produced. In order to achieve a stoichiometric SiC compound, small particle Si powder was also added to compensate the excess carbon from the pitch.

The density of the SiC foam foamed was 1.15 g/cm^3 . Figure 8 is an SEM micrograph showing a typical microstructure for the SiC foams. From this micrograph, it was observed that the SiC had a closed pore microstructure. Furthermore, the ligaments in the foam are formed from micron sized SiC grains. These grains are held together by slight sintering, which results in porous ligament with submicron size cavities or multigrain junctions. Figure 9 is a XRD showing the SiC foam is single phase.

Figure 8: SEM micrograph showing the microstructure of the SiC foam.

Figure 9: XRD showing the single phase of SiC foam.

In work using carbon/graphite foam, it was demonstrated that crushing the foam surface produces a very durable surface for applying coatings and producing an optical polish. Desirably, it was found that SiC foam could be crushed very similarly to carbon foam and produce a dense surface without powdering. The desire is that any surface voids that remain from the crushing will be filled by the pre-ceramic precursor that produces SiC after pyrolysis.

A SiC foam was surface polished and evaluated for mirror applications. Figure 10 is a schematic cross section that represents the functionally graded SiC mirror structure. Three SEM micrographs are attached to this schematic that describe the microstructure and the key features of the SiC foam. The fabrication methodology consists of an infiltration of the SiC foam with a pre-ceramic polymer followed by pressing and heat treating to $1800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. Separate sections of foam are similarly treated at higher pressures that provide the gradation in density. The impregnation of the preceramic polymer provides a seamless transition and glue for binding the

variable density sections together. Chemical Vapor Infiltration (CVI) of SiC is next performed to fill the surface pores of the dense top section of the foam. The pore sizes at the optical surface are within 1 to 3 microns. For comparison, bottom surface pore size as shown in Figure 10 is in the 100 to 200 micron range. Thus, the functional graded porosity in this case ranges from about 100 μm to 1 μm . Figure 11 shows the polished surface, which exhibits about 500 nm peak to valley (P/V).

Figure 10: Schematic and SEM micrograph showing the FGM cross-section.

Figure 11: Polished CVD-SiC Interferogram.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the above results and discussion, the following conclusions can be reached:

1. Refined coal tar pitch (CTP1) shows comparable decomposition characteristic to AR pitch.
2. The compressive strength shows strong density dependence for both AR and CTP1 pitch foams. Using CTP1, a compressive strength of 4000 psi can be obtained by foaming to a high density (0.8 g/cm^3).
3. Thermal conductivity of 215 W/mK in the Z-direction has been successfully achieved after heat treating the high density AR pitch foam at $3000 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$. The thermal conductivity is about 60 W/mK in the X-Y plane.
4. A fully dense copper/graphite-foam was produced with pressure assisted infiltration. The MMC has a density of 1.85 g/cm^3 . The thermal conductivity are about 150, 150, 350 in the X, Y, and Z directions and the CTE is about $5.5 \times 10^{-6}/^\circ\text{C}$.
5. CTP is advantageous as one component in the precursor for making SiC foam. A FGM SiC foam in conjunction with a CVI/CVD surface seal approach can yield a high quality optical surface.

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